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COGNITIVE DEVELOPMENT OF AUTIST STUDENTS: A CASE STUDY ABOUT THE SUPPORT TEACHER AT COLÉGIO ESTADUAL DE GOIATUBA (GO)

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ABSTRACT

Autism is among the Autistic Spectrum Disorders (ASD) most present in people, it is usually detected in childhood and, mainly, when the child starts his school life. Autistic disorders are complex neurological disorders that affect the acquisition of diverse skills throughout life. To be able to help students reach their full potential, it is necessary to understand this disorder and its characteristics, as well as the essential elements for this student to achieve school success. This article aimed to analyze whether students with Autistic Spectrum Disorder can develop their cognitive skills in the school context and the importance of the Support teacher in this process. The methodology used was a qualitative approach and case study, the instruments used were the observation report and a semi-structured interview with the Support teacher and with the teachers of the Portuguese Language and Mathematics subjects. The study concluded that understanding the feelings of the autistic is essential for success in learning to happen, however, the teachers of the curricular subjects do not have training aimed at teaching this group and, much less, availability in the classroom to do so, as generally the rooms are overcrowded, and it becomes impossible to get the individualized attention they need. In this way, the Support teacher is the key piece for learning to take place. Future studies should be more comprehensive and address all students diagnosed with autism in state, municipal, and private schools to understand the importance and essentiality of the Support teacher, since, sometimes, the school system itself has the belief that the regent teacher could teach this student, thus making the presence of the Support teacher unnecessary.

Keywords: Autistic Spectrum Disorder. Autism. Support Teacher. Cognitive. Development.

INTRODUCTION

The term autism, derived from the German autism and the Greek autus meaning “self”, was first introduced by the Swiss psychiatrist Eugen Bleuler in 1911 to describe schizophrenic symptomatology in adult patients (social withdrawal with interior withdrawal). From 1943, Leo Kanner used this term to differentiate it from schizophrenia, then the subject of numerous American studies that sought to base child psychiatry on the Bleulerian entity.

Kanner’s study was, of course, groundbreaking, but it is also important to note that even earlier descriptions of children who probably had autism were done in the 1800s at a training school for the intellectually disabled and in the 1700s with some reports of wild children.

Michael Rutter, a leading child psychiatric researcher at Maudsley Hospital in the United Kingdom who conducted the first genetic study of autism, stated in 1972 that “the autistic child has a fantasy deficiency rather than an excess” (RUTTER, 1983, p. 514).). The meaning of the word autism was then radically reformulated from describing someone who fantasized excessively to someone who did not fantasize at all.

The researcher followed an autistic student in the 6th grade of Elementary School in the final year at the school, which works as a high school teacher. At the time, the researcher presented Elisio Joaquim de Vasconcelos, in Goiatuba, to the management group of the State College of the Military Police of the State of Goiás – Elisio Joaquim de Vasconcelos, her research project and what motivated the choice of such a theme. On that occasion, the principal, the coordinator and the Support teacher, as well as the Portuguese Language and Mathematics teachers, authorized both the research and the monitoring of the student during the classes of the aforementioned disciplines.

METHODOLOGICAL FRAMEWORK

The observational study was carried out with an autistic student studying in the 6th of Elementary School at the State College of the Military Police of the State of Goiás – Elisio Joaquim de Vasconcelos, in Goiatuba, Goiás. This school unit was chosen because it is the field of work of the researcher,

which facilitated the design of the research. It was instituted by Law nº 18.967 of 07/22/2015, located at Rua São Paulo nº 816, Centro, in the city of Goiatuba – Goiás.

This research is descriptive of the observational type. Observational studies allow for adapting to the specific needs of each investigation. However, in general terms, an observational study of the longitudinal category.

For the elaboration of this study, bibliographical research was carried out in Portuguese, English and Spanish with the keywords: autism, learning, and teacher of Support, since this review made it possible to summarize the research already completed and to obtain conclusions from the proposed theme. In addition to the bibliographic research, observation reports and interviews were used with the Support teacher, Luciana, and the Portuguese Language and Mathematics teachers.

The report refers to a statement, written or oral, that describes the qualities, characteristics and context of some event. It is, therefore, an orderly elaboration based on observation and analysis. The purpose of preparing a report is highly variable, although it always presupposes the eventual need to inform others about something that happened (BRÁNEZ, 2013).

RESULTS ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

The research was carried out with 1 (one) student diagnosed with autism. Thus, a non-participant observation was carried out in which the researcher accompanied the student and the teacher from August to December 2019. The data were presented in the form of observation reports. The author spoke with the Mathematics and Portuguese teachers, the most critical subjects for Márcio, and with the Support teacher who accompanies the student.

During my observations I paid close attention to communication and language problems, I know that there is a strong sensory component involved in the difficulty of people with autism in developing a two-way and functional model of communication. These factors related to sensory disorders have a strong impact on language acquisition, intellectual development, behaviour and social interaction. There is profuse scientific literature on the subject, both at the auditory and motor level, as well as in

the processing of this information.

With the research carried out, it can be said that autism is still under study since there are many differences between theorists in the field of science. The information found here may shed some light on what the world of a child with autism is like.

Another point analyzed is in line with what was stated as a hypothesis: "It is considered that the limitations of the autistic student may not be of a cognitive nature, that is, he can develop more one area of knowledge than another, therefore, the teacher does not must limit it must, yes, try it in all areas of knowledge: languages and technologies, exact and human".

"The Support teacher plays a fundamental role in the development of the autistic student, as he is dealing directly with this student and with his emotions and limitations".

One of the authors (BARBERINI, 2016) confirms the hypothesis when he said that autistic children can develop different abilities than children with normal development. They may also develop skills in a different order than other children. Regarding the role of the Support teacher, it is to guarantee the presence, participation and evolution of students with disabilities in the classroom, without exception. Maturana and Mendes (2015), citing research carried out by Takala et al. (2009) in Finland, defined three different situations based on three alternative support approaches:

The first approach: individualized teaching - Was found to be effective in providing individual attention, but raised concerns for three different reasons: the pressure that could be put on supported students, the lack of contact between these students and the rest of the class, and the stigma of being separated from the common context.

The second approach: teaching in small groups - Was considered favourable due to the possibility of offering support in a peaceful environment, but also raised concerns about how some students

suffered when they were removed from their peers. They felt stigmatized and missed out on what was worked on in the regular classroom. Teaching in small groups did not offer the possibility of sufficient individual attention. To avoid this stigma and minimize the difference. In research carried out in the classroom to include children with autism, Lindsay et al. (2014) observed the benefits of having a mix of different children with the Support teacher to do some tasks. The criterion was never the level of the children: any child could receive additional help.

Goffman (1982) emphasized that prejudices structure what one person imagines of the other, which in the face of someone with a stigma defines him or her as partially human. According to the author, one way to camouflage the perception of the stigmatized person is to use subterfuges by pointing out other differences. Thus, a stigma theory is constructed, an ideology to explain their inferiority and without realizing the danger it represents, sometimes rationalizing the animosity based on other differences, such as social class.

The stigma attributed to people with disabilities and ASD is not only about what is visible in their physical characteristics but mainly with the aforementioned condition, associated with another, resulting in the stigma of inferiority, disability and discrimination. These are constructed under a socially elaborated standard of judgment based on normative expectations. The third approach: collaborative teaching with two teachers - It was the modality with the best results and most preferred by teachers. In this approach, more children could have access to support and this allowed them to remain in the classroom without losing any content (MATURANA; MENDES, 2015).

From an inclusive perspective, the Support teacher changes roles from focusing on individual rehabilitation-oriented attention to sharing class time and responsibilities with all students in the group along with the class teacher, and to sharing class time classes and activities between two teachers and improving the overall response to student diversity.

Huguet (2009) emphasizes that it is necessary to agree all together about activities, groupings, spatial distribution and so on. Second, teachers need to agree on the type of participation each will have in activities and their involvement in student assessment. Third, while the scope of activities can be broad enough to address diversity, consideration should be given to the participation of children with more learning difficulties and ensure that they receive the attention they need from their primary teacher or teacher. of support. Finally, the entire experience must be evaluated to plan possible changes and improvements.

Thus, to talk about the autistic child in the school context, it was necessary to quote Wallon, Piaget and Vygotsky, as the authors talk about the development of the human being in general, and every child needs stimuli from the environment to develop. and school is a very stimulating environment, and this stimulus is even more important for children with Autistic Spectrum Disorder. As for the family, another author, Lima (2019), referred to this group as the initial stimulus group for children with autism and that the functions of people with autism are: to care for and ensure their survival, educate them and train them to live in the social community to which they belong.

About the perception of the student I followed, I realized that he learns effectively when the support teacher uses concrete materials, and the main challenge for him is dealing with emotions. Another factor is the routine, the autistic student has to have a systematic routine because anything that escapes from it, the student changes his mood and when he is in an altered mood, he does not learn and does not fix what is being exposed to him.

CONCLUSION

Working on the theme “Autism in the school context: the relevance of the Support teacher”, represented a personal challenge from the perspective of the authors addressed here and the researcher’s vision about the challenges of Special Education. And in response to the hypotheses raised, the researcher can state that the autistic student can develop cognitive skills independent of the disorder and that the presence of a Support

teacher is essential for the school insertion process to be effective.

The authors made important contributions regarding legislation that, in a way, protects students with various disabilities, including students with Autistic Spectrum Disorder. In addition to the laws, another point observed was the presence of the family in the life of the autistic, even though several authors defend the importance of the family in the social insertion of the autistic, I believe that the lack of socialization does not depend on the family environment, it is usually of neurological origin, rather than contrary to other people with disabilities who intervene in family dynamics and the socialization process.

Thus, the importance of the Support teacher is notorious and fundamental. If each student learns differently, the autistic needs even more individualized attention, not only to teach but to listen. Understanding his feelings and often really being the one who supports him, who values his achievements and who is close to when he feels insecure or afraid.

In this way, it is considered that with increasingly crowded classrooms and with more autistic students, debating the importance of this professional is very relevant since he is fundamental for the development of the autistic, and one of the greatest difficulties of autism begins in verbal development. and language. Having a professional able to listen, understand, support and individualize the teaching process with a specific focus on the student and their individual needs, cognitive development becomes concrete. The fundamental thing is that, in addition to the potential of each autistic, it is that in their environment they find support, encouragement and the necessary ways to build their integrity, with new learning that will provide them with the necessary tools for personal development, which is inclusive in the context in which it operates.

It is possible to integrate and include autistic people both in school and social spaces, as well as in family spaces, their progress will depend on how the teacher will work with them, not limiting how much they learned, but the quality of what was learned, that is, showing within of his activities, his posture at home and school, such

as how to fit his school supplies in his backpack, collect and store the materials or toys he has used, or help with household chores, such as organizing the room he occupies, help the mother to set the table, among other tasks.

On the one hand, the articulation of actions within the Inclusive Special Education modality must be strengthened to facilitate the support that students with autism require to achieve the curricular objectives proposed by the school, facilitating an effective social integration and, on the other hand, the integration these students through actions articulated with the levels and other modalities of the National Education System.

The study showed that the targeted and individualized support of an education professional is essential for students with autism to develop their academic skills. If each student learns differently, the autistic needs even more individualized attention, not only to learn curricular and academic activities but also to learn to listen and understand command voices.

The study concluded that understanding the feelings of the autistic is essential for success in learning to happen, however, the teachers of the curricular subjects do not have training aimed at teaching this group and, much less, availability in the classroom to do so, as generally the rooms are overcrowded and it becomes impossible to get the individualized attention they need. In this way, the Support teacher is the key piece for learning to take place.

Future studies should be more comprehensive and address all students diagnosed with autism in state, municipal and private schools to understand the importance and essentiality of the Support teacher, since, sometimes, the school system itself has the belief that the regent teacher can teach this student, thus making the presence of the Support teacher unnecessary.

RECOMMENDATIONS

- Carry out courses, workshops and seminars for understanding between Asperger's and autism.
- Carry out workshops or training courses in special education and preparation of curricular

and pedagogical adaptations, etc. In and for effective inclusive education, at least once a year, at the beginning of each administration.

- Each classroom should not only have a class teacher, but also a permanent assistant who can help students diagnosed with autism.

- Each student diagnosed with autism must have a Support teacher in the classroom so that they have a more personalized learning process so that the results are optimal and are reflected in their school performance.

- Teachers, in particular, should seek information in the different means of communication so that they have more knowledge about the needs, forms and rhythms of learning that students with a diagnosis of autism have.

- Teachers, without exception, must make curricular and didactic adaptations, from planning to development in the classroom, lesson by lesson.

- Hold courses, workshops or seminars for teachers and parents so that they have more knowledge on how to help in the process of adaptation, not only educationally, but also socially and culturally, of children diagnosed with autism.

- Another very important recommendation is that the Ministry of Education establish fixed qualitative parameters to describe and classify the school performance of these children diagnosed with autism on a scale, such as: good, very good, medium, and bad, from the interview with the teachers and the director, there is no qualitative parameter regulated by the ministry.

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